

DURABILITY OF SODA-LIME-SILICATE GLASSES. PART I.

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The variation of durability of glasses with different compositions and the effect of minute traces of impurities present in the materials on the durability have been studied. A suitable range through which the compositions of the glasses may be varied without seriously impairing durability has been worked out. It has been established that for identical durability a number of glass compositions is possible.

The evil effects of glass ware of low durability have been reported by various workers (Richmond, *Analyst*, 1923, 48, 260; Bodenstein, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1894, 18, 116; Kooij, *ibid.*, 1893, 12, 155; Berthelot, *Compt. rend.*, 1897, 125, 271; 1905, 140, 1266; Mellor, "Chemical Statics and Dynamics", 1904, p. 57; Bone and Wheeler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 81, 538). Poor durability of glass is primarily due to imperfect composition of the batch mixture. A simple stable glass usually contains silica, an alkaline oxide and a stabilising dibasic or a tribasic oxide. Many attempts have been made to find out the best ratio between the oxides in glass in order to obtain maximum durability (Travers, *J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1921, 8, 200; Knapp, *ibid.*, 1926, 10, 294; Peddle, *ibid.*, 1921, 8, 195; Hodkin and Turner, *ibid.*, 1920, 4, 120). Also, many formulae have been advanced to represent the best durable glass, but, the formula, $6\text{SiO}_2 \cdot \text{R}'_2\text{O} \cdot \text{R}''\text{O}$ (where $\text{R}'\text{O}$ represents a molecule of either sodium oxide or potassium oxide and $\text{R}''\text{O}$, a molecule of any of the dibasic oxides) advanced by Benrath (Peddle, "Defects in Glass", p. 205, 1927) has received wide attention as being the most suitable for soda-lime glasses. According to Benrath's formula, a soda-lime-silica glass should have 75.4% silica, 12.9% sodium oxide and 11.7% calcium oxide. The compositions of commercial soda-lime-silica glasses of standard durability approximate very closely to the values calculated above. This no doubt lends strong support in favour of Benrath's formula for a tri-silicate glass. It, however, appears erroneous to accept the above as a general formula for various reasons. Firstly, the durability of glass, as pointed out previously, is a function of the percentages of the constituent oxides, and this may be expressed mathematically as, $D = [(\% \text{R}'_2\text{O})(\% \text{R}''\text{O})(\% \text{SiO}_2)]$, where D stands for durability.

It follows from mathematical analysis that it is quite reasonable to obtain the same fixed value for "D" by properly varying the variables. This aspect of the problem, which is of fundamental importance, seems to have been overlooked by Benrath. Secondly, there will hardly be any uniformity in respect of durability between two glasses, prepared according to Benrath's formula, if materials of commercial quality and chemically pure ingredients be used. Thirdly, glasses containing 75.4% silica are liable to develop "silica devitrification stones", more particularly during working with these glasses (Knote, *Trans. Amer. Cer. Soc.*, 1912, 14, 655).

The present investigation has been undertaken with the following specific objects -

- (1) To study the variations in durability with different compositions and eventually to show that for identical durability a number of compositions is possible.
- (2) To indicate a suitable range through which the composition may be varied without seriously affecting the durability. According to Benrath's formula, a single com-

position will give a durable glass, but it is not often practicable to adhere strictly to a definite composition, as slight variations must take place even in the same factory owing to diverse reasons.

(3) To study the effects of minute impurities associating the raw materials and those derived from the pots or tanks. It may be pointed out at this stage that these impurities, even in minute traces, contribute substantially towards the formation of a more durable glass.

Four series of soda-lime-silica glasses were melted and in each series percentage of silica was kept constant, while successive amounts of Na_2O were replaced by lime. While selecting a composition due consideration was made regarding the possibility of founding the glass under commercially attainable furnace temperature and each specimen was prepared, as far as practicable, under identical conditions.

In order to test the durability of glasses recourse was taken to 'Powder test' (Faraday, *Phil. Trans.*, 1830, p. 49; Pelouze, *Compt. rend.*, 1856, 43, 117; Mylius and Foerster *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1092; *Z. Instrum.*, 1889, 9, 120; Hagmaier, *Met. Chem. Eng.*, 1917, 16, 604; Nicolardot, *Compt. rend.*, 1919, 169, 335; Peddle, *J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1920, 4, 3, 299; 1921, 5, 72, 195). According to Peddle (*loc. cit.*) this test is of special value in working out a new glass, when the durabilities of a series of 'like' glasses have to be examined: as it shows in a remarkable manner the effect of the substitution of known amounts of a given constituent upon durability. The results of 'Powder test' are expressed in mg. of sulphuric acid required to neutralise the filtrate after boiling 100 g. of glass powder of 160 mesh sieve. Only on special occasions 'Autoclave test' (Lesure, *J. Pharm. chim.*, 1910, 1, 66; Nicolardot, *Compt. rend.*, 1916, 163, 355; Bishchowsky, *J. Amer. Cer. Soc.*, 1920, 3, 296; Baillie and Wilson, *J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1922, 6, 279; *J. Inst. Chem.*, 1920, p. 202), as also fuming hydrochloric acid test (Walker, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 27, 865; Nicolardot, *loc. cit.*, Turner, *J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1917, 1, 153; 1918, 2, 219; 1919, 3, 228) were also applied.

An interesting phenomenon was observed in connection with the determination of sulphuric acid value. If the glass powder left after the acid value determination be exposed to atmosphere for overnight, it again gives a sulphuric acid value. This is more pronounced with glasses rich in Na_2O . This aspect of the problem, however, is under investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Each batch was intimately mixed and its quantity was so adjusted as to yield 100 g. of finished glass. For each melt a separate Morgan fire-clay crucible was used. The crucible was at first introduced empty in a furnace and maintained at a temperature of $1350^\circ \pm 25^\circ$. The batch was introduced when the crucible attained the furnace temperature and the heating was continued till the metal was almost plained. At this stage the crucible with its contents was allowed to cool slowly in the furnace. This procedure facilitates observation of the tendency of the glass towards devitrification. When cold, the crucible was broken and the glass taken out.

Table I shows the purity of the raw materials used and Table II gives the compositions of the glasses studied.

TABLE I

Material.	Source.	SiO ₂ .	Fe ₂ O ₃ .	Al ₂ O ₃ .	CaO.	MgO.	Na ₂ CO ₃ .	NaCl & Na ₂ SO ₄ .	Loss.
Sand	Banda, (Allahabad)	98.9%	0.2%	0.2%	Slight trace	Slight trace	—	—	0.5%
Lime	Katni	3.1%	0.9%	2.1%	65.3%	0.2%	—	—	—
Heavy soda ash	I. C. I.	—	—	—	Slight trace	Slight trace	96.8%	Trace	3.1%

TABLE II

Series.	Batch No.	Batch mixture (in g.)			% Composition.			Calculated in the form of a mol. formula representing Na ₂ O as unity.	Remarks
		Sand.	Soda.	Lime.	SiO ₂ .	Na ₂ O.	CaO.		
A	1	73.66	34.09	18.35	73	15	12	Na ₂ O. 0.89 CaO. 5.07 SiO ₂	Clear, no devitrification
	2	73.66	31.81	19.9	73	14	13	Na ₂ O. 1.03 CaO. 5.4 SiO ₂	Do
	3	73.66	29.54	21.4	73	13	14	Na ₂ O. 1.2 CaO. 5.85 SiO ₂	Do
	4	73.66	28.4	22.2	73	12.5	14.5	Na ₂ O. 1.29 CaO. 6.04 SiO ₂	Do
	5	73.66	20.72	23.73	73	11.5	15.5	Na ₂ O. 1.5 CaO. 6.57 SiO ₂	Do
	6	73.66	18.01	25.03	73	10	17	Na ₂ O. 1.88 CaO. 7.55 SiO ₂	Slight seedlings
	7	73.66	14.33	26.33	73	8	19	Na ₂ O. 2.61 CaO. 9.35 SiO ₂	Did not melt clearly
	9	73.66	29.72	16.07	73	16.5	10.5	Na ₂ O. 0.7 CaO. 4.57 SiO ₂	Clear, no devitrification
	10	73.66	31.53	14.54	73	17.5	9.5	Na ₂ O. 0.6 CaO. 4.31 SiO ₂	Do
	11	73.66	33.33	13.01	73	18.5	8.5	Na ₂ O. 0.5 CaO. 4.05 SiO ₂	Do
	B	12	70.77	31.53	19.14	70	17.5	12.5	Na ₂ O. 0.8 CaO. 4.13 SiO ₂
13		70.77	28.8	21.4	70	16	14	Na ₂ O. 0.96 CaO. 4.48 SiO ₂	Do
14		70.77	27.0	23.0	70	15	15	Na ₂ O. 1.1 CaO. 4.83 SiO ₂	Do
15		70.77	22.5	26.6	70	12.5	17.5	Na ₂ O. 1.54 CaO. 5.77 SiO ₂	Do
C	16	74.8	31.8	13	74	17.5	8.5	Na ₂ O. 0.53 CaO. 4.37 SiO ₂	Do
	17	74.8	29.09	15.3	74	16	10	Na ₂ O. 0.7 CaO. 4.77 SiO ₂	Do
	18	74.8	27.09	16.84	74	15	11	Na ₂ O. 0.81 CaO. 5.11 SiO ₂	Do
	19	74.8	22.7	20.68	74	12.5	13.5	Na ₂ O. 1.1 CaO. 6.13 SiO ₂	Do
D	20	75.8	31.8	11.5	75	17.5	7.5	Na ₂ O. 0.47 CaO. 4.43 SiO ₂	Slight seedlings
	21	75.8	29.09	13.8	75	16	9	Na ₂ O. 0.62 CaO. 4.84 SiO ₂	Do

The sulphuric acid value of each specimen was determined separately in accordance with the specification given under "Powder test" (*loc. cit.*). Only in a few cases the 'autoclave' and the 'fuming hydrochloric acid' tests were performed. Table III shows the results thus obtained, and it also indicates the effect of substitution of known amounts of Na₂O by lime on durability. It is to be noted that the proportion of Na₂O can only be decreased up to a minimum beyond which the glass becomes too much refractory. For the sake of comparison, the sulphuric acid values of Pyrex glass, 'Sico' glass, 'Sigcol' glass and a specimen of Indian bottle glass have also been included in the table.

It may be pointed out that resistant glass for chemical ware gives with the "powder test", a sulphuric acid value of about 100. A good soda-lime-silica glass gives a value about 600 (Peddle, "Defects in Glass", p. 195). On this basis it will be evident from Table III that with the exception of sample A-11, C-16 and D-20, all other samples are durable glasses. For the sake of convenience the compositions of the durable glasses have been

represented in Fig. 1 by a tri-axial diagram and any composition within the area of the rectangle will give a durable glass.

FIG. 1.

TABLE III

Series.	Batch No.	H ₂ SO ₄ value.	Loss in wt. after refluxing with HCl.	pH of aq. extract after autoclaving.
A	{ 1	235	1.5%	8.6
	{ 2	225		
	{ 3	186		
	{ 4	154	2	
	{ 5	119	3.4	
	{ 6	93		
{ 9	320			
B	{ 10	578	3.7	9.0
	{ 11	879		
	{ 12	479		
	{ 13	399		
C	{ 14	303	3.1	2.0
	{ 15	164		
	{ 16	763		
	{ 17	506		
D	{ 18	290	2.1	10.0
	{ 19	156		
	{ 20	753		
	{ 21	580		
Pyrox glass		24		
'Sigoal' glass		33		
'Sico' glass (Germany)		29		
Indian glass bottle		1160		

With a view to establishing our primary object recourse has been taken to the graphic method. Figure 2 is a graphic representation of the results shown in Table III. Four curves have been obtained by plotting H₂SO₄ values against the % Na₂O of each series, as the durability of glass depends more particularly on its alkali content. In order to

ascertain the composition of the glass corresponding to any point on these curves, the silica content is directly read off from the curve, the Na_2O content is obtained from the abscissa of the point and the CaO content is obtained by difference. Now, if from a point on the ordinate, corresponding to a particular H_2SO_4 value, a straight line be drawn parallel to the abscissa, this line will cut the curves at different points. The H_2SO_4 value of the glasses of compositions corresponding to these points should be identical and in this way any number of lines of equal durability may be drawn from the ordinate. This line of equal durability is analogous to the line of equal melting temperature (isotherms) of Morey and Bowen (*J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1925, 9, 226) and to lines of equal viscosity (log isokoms of Washburn, Shelton and Libman, Bull. University of Illinois, No. 140, April 14, 1924).

FIG. 2.

In order to substantiate the above deduction it may be pointed out that if a line be drawn from the point corresponding to a H_2SO_4 value of 580, it will cut the curves at three points. The compositions of the glasses corresponding to two of these points are already known (Batch Nos. A-10 & D-21). The H_2SO_4 values, as actually found out, are 578 and 580 respectively. The same identity will be found with batches bearing Nos. A-4 and C-19. Again, Table IV shows the calculated compositions of glasses corresponding to an acid value of 400 (Fig. 2) and to values actually determined. Further work in this direction is in progress.

TABLE V

% Composition			Acid value	
SiO_2	Na_2O	CaO	Calc.	Observed.
70	16	14	400	399
73	17	10	400	404
7	15.8	10.4	400	401

In order to study the effect of impurities on durability of glass, soda-lime-silica glasses of another series were melted, starting with pure ingredients. In the present case reagent quality anhydrous sodium carbonate, precipitated chalk and purified sand were used. The quantity of each batch was so adjusted as to yield 25 g. of finished glass and this was melted in a platinum crucible under identical conditions. For the sake of a comparative study the compositions were selected from those given in Table II. The glasses were then subjected to 'powder test'. It will be clear from Table V that the impurities, even in minute traces, exert a considerable influence on the durability of glass. The sulphuric acid value is almost double in each case.

TABLE VI

Batch No.	% Composition.			H_2SO_4 value of glass from	
	SiO_2	Na_2O	CaO	commercial material.	pure material.
A-1	73	15	12	235	408
B-14	70	15	15	303	817
C-17	74	16	10	506	793
D-21	76	16	9	580	1038

DISCUSSION

From Fig. 2 it is evident that each curve has a steep portion of its own. This indicates how rapidly the durability changes with change of Na_2O content and after this the rate of change is not very appreciable. The various compositions corresponding to the steep portion of each curve will be of special advantage to glass manufacturers. Because, in order to take the best advantage of decreasing alkali content, without at the same time impairing appreciably the melting and working qualities of glass, the manufacturer can utilise any composition represented by the steep portion of the curves. The composition, however, is to be so selected as to yield a glass of low sulphuric acid value.

Secondly, the lines of equal durability will offer to the manufacturers a number of possible compositions for founding a glass of desired durability. From these they will be able to select a particular composition consistent with the furnace efficiency and with the viscosity required in working the metal.

The effect of impurities on durability of glass is evident from Table V. It is sufficiently clear that a dibasic oxide alone cannot confer a desired durability on a simple glass consisting of silica and an alkaline oxide. The presence of a slight trace of a tri-basic oxide is essential.

Lastly, referring to the different tests in vogue for testing the durability of glass it is claimed that though these tests give different values they, however, follow the same order. But from our findings we could not corroborate the statement.

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